

NFDI4Earth

Report

Learning about user perspectives beyond the Earth System Sciences

Lessons learned from a workshop on finding and sharing environmental, climate, and urban data

Anna Brauer

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Executive Summary

During Love Data Week, the Come2Data project hosted a series of talks and workshops in the Open Science Lab of SLUB Dresden, promoting topics in research data management. Our contribution, entitled *"Data Makes the Earth Go Round: Finding and Sharing Environmental, Climate, and Urban Data"*, introduced the audience to the central services developed by NFDI4Earth. Through a use case on urban climate and heat adaptation, we demonstrated how to locate relevant datasets and discussed common challenges in data search, access, and usage.

In the following hands-on session, the participants, having their own workflows and research data management challenges in mind, explored the OneStop4All portal as the central access point to the NFDI4Earth services. The feedback we gathered will support our ongoing efforts to improve the usability and utility of our services for our community. As the audience consisted predominantly of experts from history, library science, and research data management, the workshop also provided valuable insights into the expectations of interdisciplinary user groups, which are particularly relevant in the context of the broader transition toward a common and linked NFDI approach (OneNFDI).

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Introduction

Love Data Week (LDW) is an international event celebrated annually to promote current topics in research data management¹. On 11 February 2026, the Come2Data project invited researchers, students, and data practitioners to a series of presentations and workshops revolving around the question “*Where’s the data?*”. The event was hosted by Sächsische Landes-, Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden (SLUB)².

NFDI4Earth contributed a workshop entitled “*Data Makes the Earth Go Round: Finding and Sharing Environmental, Climate, and Urban Data*”³ to the event. Around 25 participants were introduced to central services developed by NFDI4Earth, including the Knowledge Hub⁴, the EduTrain portal⁵, the User Support Network⁶, and the OneStop4All⁷ portal. The workshop focused on the lattermost, as the OneStop4All serves as the entry point to all services offered by NFDI4Earth, enables the discovery of resources relevant to Earth System Science (ESS), and provides guidance and information about research data management.

The workshop introduced the participants to a use case on urban climate and heat adaption⁸ to provide them with a concrete thematic example. The participants learned where to find climate data, geospatial base data, and information on urban infrastructure; typical challenges were discussed, e.g., concerning data availability and spatio-temporal coverage of the data. Furthermore, the presentation outlined how results from urban climate models can be used for planning heat-resilient cities.

The use case served as a gateway for participants to actively engage and provided a shared context to discuss data discovery and publication challenges, therefore setting the stage for the subsequent hands-on session. The participants were asked to reflect on their existing workflows for data search and data publishing, as well as associated challenges they may have encountered. With these in mind, the participants, in groups of four to six, were encouraged to explore the OneStop4All portal and investigate its functionalities.

This report documents central lessons learned from the group discussions that will support the continued improvement of the NFDI4Earth-developed services

¹ <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/sites/icpsr/about/news-events/international-love-data-week>

² The programme is available at: <https://www.slub-dresden.de/besuchen/veranstaltungen/details/veranstaltung/56545>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/18660302/>

⁴ <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/>

⁵ <https://edutrain.nfdi4earth.de/>

⁶ <https://nfdi4earth.de/2facilitate/user-support-network>

⁷ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>

⁸ Ziemann, A., Uiboupin, K., Goldberg, V. (2024): Hitzeanpassung in Städten – welche Maßnahme bringt’s? Bewertung von Umbauszenarien der grauen und grünen Infrastruktur in der Stadt Plauen. RaumPlanung 227(3/4), 12-18.

and highlight topical issues in research data management. For context, the report also provides the results of an introductory survey on the background of the workshop participants.

Understanding the audience

The workshop was explicitly designed for all interested participants, not exclusively for researchers and students from the ESS community. An activating survey at the beginning of the workshop helped us better understand participants' data practices and backgrounds. The results showed that none of the participants primarily worked with climate or environmental data; only a few individuals (16%) reported working with geospatial base data. Based on our impressions from the hands-on phase of the workshop, we concluded that the majority came from domains such as history, library science, and research data management.

Detailed results of the survey are presented below. For each question, the participants were asked to select as many of the provided options as applicable. The survey was conducted using AhaSlides⁹.

Where do participants search for data?

While *Geoportal.de*¹⁰ and *Geoportal Sachsenatlas*¹¹ were used by 10% each, most participants reported using other means for data search. Notably, a quarter indicated that they have not yet found a suitable portal where the data they are looking for is published.

Figure 1: Survey results showing where participants search for data. Options included a selection of data portals, as well as *“Ich suche ein Portal”* (“I’m looking for a portal”) and *“Sonstige”* (“Other”).

⁹ <https://ahaslides.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.geoportal.de/>

¹¹ <https://geoportal.sachsen.de/>

Where do participants publish their data?

Around 35% of the participants were not publishing their data; however, the majority of these were looking for a suitable repository (20% of all participants). The most popular publishing platform was Zenodo¹² (17%). Another 15% were publishing their data in their organization's internal repository. A small number also used the platforms OpARA¹³ (6%) and PANGAEA¹⁴ (3%). A quarter of the participants indicated that they published their data on other platforms not listed in the survey.

Figure 2: Results from the survey showing where participants publish data. Options included the platforms OpARA, PANGAEA, and Zenodo, as well as "Ich suche ein Repository" ("I'm looking for a repository"), "Lokale Speicherung" ("Local storage"), "Internes Repository" ("Internal repository"), and "Sonstige" ("Other").

Lessons learned

The concept of the OneStop4All portal as a central access point for environmental and Earth system data was clearly welcomed by the participants, and the strategic direction it is headed in was generally well-received. Suggestions for improvement focused on usability, discoverability, and the range of the searchable resources.

Lesson 1: Personal support remains essential

The participants emphasized the importance of an easily accessible, human-centered support structure. They welcomed the concept of the User Support Network as an access point to the support structures of participating NFDI4Earth

¹² <https://zenodo.org/>

¹³ <https://opara.zih.tu-dresden.de/>

¹⁴ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

partners, and positively noted its accessibility through the contact form in the OneStop4All portal.

Lesson 2: Demand for interdisciplinary and historical data

A recurring theme throughout the workshop was the strong interest in data beyond classical Earth system domains. In particular, participants highlighted data from the energy sector (e.g., renewable energy potential), which are relevant in multidisciplinary contexts, and historical flood maps. While flood-related information is clearly within the scope of Earth System Science, historical map material can provide valuable complementary evidence, for example for the reconstruction of past events or the validation of models. This shows the potential of integrating historical data more systematically into Earth System Science workflows within NFDI4Earth.

Lesson 3: Importance of usability, clarity, and convenience

Some participants expressed the desire to obtain data more directly by being able to download datasets without having to navigate through several detail pages. Another usability-related issue that was raised concerned elements of the user interface that may not be self-explanatory to all user groups (e.g., the spatial search via map interface). For these elements, the participants recommend providing short tutorials or illustrative examples.

Lesson 4: Need for data quality indicators

While the NFDI4Earth Label¹⁵ for data repositories was regarded positively, participants expressed the need for a more differentiated assessment of both data and metadata quality. This includes aspects such as adherence to discipline-specific standards and conventions, completeness of metadata, as well as information on measurement accuracy and associated uncertainties. Rather than a single aggregated score, participants highlighted the importance of providing multiple, transparent indicators that reflect different dimensions of quality. Suggested approaches ranged from standardized quality metrics (e.g., inspired by existing frameworks for data and metadata quality assessment) to more intuitive visualizations, such as icons or traffic-light systems. In particular, making uncertainties visible and understandable during data discovery was considered essential. Overall, the discussion emphasized that quality information should be clearly communicated and easily interpretable, while still allowing users to access more detailed underlying assessments if needed.

¹⁵ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/label>

Lesson 5: Semantic linking could enhance search functionality

Participants suggested that semantic linking could improve the search experience. As an example, they proposed that the keyword “noise” could also yield results related to air quality or environmental monitoring in general. This discussion was sparked by a group’s unsuccessful search for noise maps covering the area of Dresden.

Lesson 6: Useful filter options include standards, data type, CRS, and temporal coverage

The temporal coverage of the data was repeatedly mentioned as being more relevant for data search than the publication date, which is currently offered as a filter option. Further filter options that were identified as desirable, in order of relevance by stated importance and request frequency, are: data type, data standards, and the coordinate reference system of static maps.

Lesson 7: Agentic and generative AI cause concerns about resilience and user privacy

The OneStop4All Chatbot prompted a discussion on resilience and privacy in the context of generative and agentic AI. Currently, it is not evident to the users whether conversations with the chatbot are recorded and stored by the portal. Moreover, participants were interested in whether AI resilience was part of the repository assessment for the NFDI4Earth Label. They noted that data providers and aggregators are increasingly considering measures such as access controls to protect their services from excessive automated requests.

Summary

The Love Data Week workshop demonstrated that the services of NFDI4Earth can provide value to a broad range of user groups across and beyond disciplines of the Earth System Sciences, representing an opportunity to position the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All portal as an entry point for interdisciplinary data discovery and reuse. This was illustrated by the example of historical maps, which are relevant for social scientists and historians, but could also provide the Earth System Sciences with data from periods for which empirical records are limited. Interdisciplinary use cases are becoming more prominent, as an increasing number of research projects rely on data from multiple disciplines to enable collaborative and cross-domain knowledge production. As a consequence, NFDI4Earth services will need to address increasingly diverse user groups with differing data cultures, expectations, and search strategies. For this, usability, clearly defined and consistently applied terminology, and accessible support structures are decisive factors for long-term success. As for data to truly “make the Earth go round,” they must not only exist, they must be findable, understandable, and accessible.